

2002 ARCSS Community Leadership Teleconference | Agenda

ARCSS COMMITTEE AND ARCSS COMMUNITY LEADERSHIP TELECONFERENCE

13 August 2002

Agenda

Tuesday, August 13

1. Welcome

1. Jonathan Overpeck, ARCSS Committee Chair
2. Neil Swanberg, Acting ARCSS Program Manager

2. ARCSS Committee Part 1: Responsibilities

1. Discussion of proposed major activity item for AC: Arctic System Synthesis

1. Not a major program reorganization
2. Goals of ARCSS still focused on "useful science" and providing the knowledge for society to deal with arctic environmental variability and change
3. Focus on synthesis within themes, but also between ? looking at the arctic as one system
4. Payoffs will hopefully include: intellectual breakthroughs, increased rate of high-profile papers, enhanced interdisciplinary synergy, better roadmap for ARCSS, stronger funding support for ARCSS, greater service to society.

3. Finalizing the 2002 ARCSS All Hands Workshop Report

1. One key input to synthesis

4. Outstanding Issues

1. Identification and listing (seeking community input on what should be dealt with at AC meeting in Fall 02)

5. ARCSS Committee Part 2: Governance, Meetings, etc.

1. Membership: representation, terms of office, rotation, call for nominations
2. Establishment of Executive Committee
3. Meeting participation and agendas

1. rotate DC/Non-DC annual meetings
2. regular use of executive sessions at beginning and ends of meetings

6. Final Word - AC Chair is open to input.